

SIDDHA HERBO MINERAL FORMULATION LINGA BOOPATHI MATHIRAI
- A DRUG REVIEW

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ABSTRACT:

The traditional Siddha medicinal approach enhances the Physical, mental, and spiritual well-being of humans. This ideology was developed by the Siddhars, who were ancient, spiritual saints from South India. Animal, Mineral, and Botanical substances that have undergone pharmaceutical processing to yield therapeutic effects make up this medicinal mixture. Linga Boopathi Mathirai(LBM) is one of such Herbo-Mineral formulation which consists of Purified Lingam (Red Sulphide of Mercury (Natural), Purified Rasa

Chenduram (Red Sulphide of Mercury), Purified Rasa Karpooram (Hydragyrum Subchloride), Omam (Carum copticum), Kaavi kal (Red Ochre), Lavangam (Syzygium aromaticum). The current review focusses on the traditional applications of LBM, as well as the scientific examination of the pharmacological actions of the components of LBM on Siddha Mineral preparations, in order to substantiate the traditional claims regarding the medicinal value of LBM.

KEYWORDS: *Linga Boopathi Mathirai*, Drug review, Siddha medicine, Herbo Mineral preparation

INTRODUCTION:

The Siddha system originated in Tamil Nadu and other regions of South India, developed by the Siddhars—ancient spiritual and mystical sages¹. Siddha system is made by siddhars who focused on holistic well being of individuals not only our body also our Mind and Soul. The Siddha system emphasize the individualized treatments. Treatment of Siddha medicine based on the *Thiridhosams, Seven Udal Thathukal, Ennvagai thervu, 96 Thathuvams*. Ingredients of Siddha Medicines consists Herbals, Metals, Minerals and Animal substances that have undergone pharmaceutical processing to yield therapeutic effects make up this medicinal mixture. Siddha medicine has 32 type of Internal medicines and 32 types of External medicines². Mathirai is one of the Internal medicines. *Linga Boopathi Mathirai*³ is one such herbo-mineral formulation that consists of purified Lingam (Red Sulphide of Mercury (Natural), purified *Rasa Chenduram*(Red Sulphide of Mercury), purified *Rasa Karpooram* (Hydragyrum Subchloride) , *Omam* (*Carum copticum*), *Kaavi kal* (Red Ochre), *Lavangam* (*Syzygium aromaticum*) which is

prescribed for the treatment of Fever and Intestinal worms. This extensive review of the herbo-mineral formulation LBM provides us with a scientific basis for prescribing it for therapeutic purposes and also helps for future studies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Research Design: Drug Review on Literature

Research Type: Literature Review

Research Period: 3 months

TABLE NO : 1 Profile of *Linga Boopathi Mathirai*⁴

S.no	Ingredients	Botanical name / Chemical name	Quantity
1	Purified <i>Lingam</i>	Red Sulphide of Mercury(Natural)	35 grams
2	Purified <i>Rasa Chendooram</i>	Red Sulphide of Mercury	35 grams
3	Purified <i>Rasa Karpooram</i>	Hydragyrum Subchloride	35 grams
4	<i>Omam</i>	<i>Carum copticum</i>	35 grams
5	<i>Kavikal</i>	Red Ochre	35 grams
6	<i>Lavangam</i>	<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i>	35 grams

Method of preparation⁴ :

After the purification grind the ingredients with water for 12 hours and make pills 2 grains size.

Indications:

- *Suram* (Fever)
- Intestinal worms

Dosage: 1-2 pills for Twice a day

Adjuvant: Honey ,Ginger juice or Breast milk.

RESULTS:**SIDDHA ASPECT OF THE LITERATURE⁵⁻⁶ :****LINGAM (RED SULPHIDE OF MERCURY(NATURAL)):**

Lingam is one of the *Pancha Sootham*. It is known as *Inguligam, Raasam, Kadaivanni, Karpam, Kaanjanam, Sandagam, Samarasam, Saaniyam, Chenduram, Maniraagam, Milecham, Vani, Vanni*. The *Lingam* we use nowadays is called 'Jathi Linga Paadana' grouped under *Vaippu Paadana*.

Taste: Tasteless and Odourless

Potency: Hot

Action: Alterative

General properties: It is effect in the treatment of diarrhoea, pyrexia, urticaria, delirium, diuresis, tuberculossis, scabiers, unknown bites, syphilis, delirium, leprosy, eczema, skin diseases, vadha diseasees and throbbing pain.

RASA CHENDOORAM (RED SULPHIDE OF MERCURY):

This is different from the *Rasa chendooram* comes under *Rasam*(mercury). It is commercially prepared by the combination of *Rasam*(Mercury) and *Gandhagam* (Sulphur). Its properties and actions are more or less similar to cinnabar. The external application prepared by using red sulphide of mercury effective in the treatment of scabies and ulcers.

RASA KARPOORAM (HYDRAGYRAM SUBCHLORIDE):

It is considered one of the *Paadanams* even though not mentioned in 64 *Paadanams*. It is made up of combination of *Rasam* and Salt. It is also called as *Pooram*.

Taste: Salty

Potency: Hot

Action: Alterative, antiseptic, sialogogue, cholagogue, laxative

General properties: Traditionally it is used for treating throbbing pain in the lumbar region, burning sensation, hepatomgaly, fever, basillary dysentery, dropsy, chronic ulcers, venereal diseases, indigestion, vomiting, diarrhoea, worm infestation, rheumatism, itching, constipation, scabies, headache.

KAAVI KAL(RED OCHRE):

It is one of the *Uparasams*. It is also called as *Poonkavi*. Red bolu vohre is a Silicate of Alumina internal and oxied of iron. It relieves bleeding from internal organs.

Taste: Astringent

Potency: Cool

Action: Anticoagulant, insecticide

General properties: Eye diseases, veneral diseases, vomiting, extensive eczema, tooth ache,herpes, gum bleeding.

OMAM (Carum copticum):

Part used: Seeds

Taste: Pungent

Potency: Hot

Action: Stomachic, antispasmodic, carminative, antiseptic, stimulant, tonic, sialogogue

General properties: Traditionally it is used for treating fever, cough, indigestion, asthma, teeth problems, diarrhoea.

LAVANGAM (Syzygium aromaticum):

Part used: Seeds

Taste: Pungent

Potency: Hot

Action: Stomachic, antispasmodic, carminative

General properties: Traditionally it is used for treating fatigue, diarrhoea, ear diseases, vomiting.

TABLE NO : 2 SCIENTIFIVE REVIEW OF HERBAL DRUGS

DRUG	SCIENTIFIC NAME	FAMILY	PHYTO CHEMICALS	PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITY
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<i>Omam</i>	<i>Carum copticum</i>	Apiaceae	Carvacrol, thymol(volatile oil), terpinene, o-cymene,paracymene, beta pinene,hexa decane, terpinolene, linoleic acid	Anti-inflammatory activity ⁷ , analgesic activity ⁸ , anthelmintic activity ⁹
<i>Lavangam</i>	<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i>	Myrtaceae	Eugenyl acetate, eugenol, beta caryophyllene, carvacral, thymol, cinnamaldehyde	Anti-inflammatory activity ¹⁰ , anthelmintic activity ¹¹ , antipyretic activity ¹²

TABLE NO : 3 SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF MINERALS INGREDIENTS IN VARIOUS FORMULATION

Medicine	Incredients of LBM	Pharmacological activity
<i>Linga chendooram</i>	<i>Lingam</i>	Antipyretic activity of <i>Linga chendooram</i> were evaluated using brewers yeast induced fever in albino rats ¹³
<i>Linga Mathirai</i>	<i>Lingam</i>	Antipyretic acativity of <i>Linga mathirai</i> were evaluated in experimental animals
<i>Ashtabhairava Mathirai</i>	<i>Lingam</i>	Antipyretic activity ¹⁴

<i>Padiga Linga Chenduram</i>	<i>Lingam</i>	Antipyretic activity
<i>Poora Parpam</i>	<i>Rasa karpooram</i>	Antipyretic activity of <i>Poora parpam</i> evaluated in rodent models ¹⁵
<i>Karpoora Chinthamani Mathirai</i>	<i>Rasa karpooram</i>	Antipyretic, analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity of <i>Karpoora Chinthamani Mathirai</i> evaluated ¹⁶
<i>Krumighattini Tablet</i>	Red ochre	In- Vitro Anthelmintic Evaluation of polyherbal Formulation: <i>Krumighattini Tablet</i> ¹⁷
<i>Shuddha Ghairik</i>	Red ochre	Antipyretic activity ¹⁸
<i>Kshara Agada</i>	Red ochre	Conceptual study on Anthelmintic action of <i>Kshara Agada</i>

DISCUSSION:

According to the review of literature on *Linga Boopathi Mathirai* (LBM), the ingredients possess multiple pharmacological activities. However, in this context, only the **Antipyretic** and **Anthelmintic** activities are highlighted, as they are directly relevant to the traditional indications of LBM. This review supports the scientific validation of LBM's therapeutic uses, particularly in relation to its antipyretic and anthelmintic properties.

In *Carum copticum*, the main constituents are thymol and carvacrol, which are primarily responsible for its anti-inflammatory activity⁷. Mohammad Hossein Dashti-Rahmatabadi et al designed and conducted an experimental clinical trial to assess and compare the analgesic effect of the ethanolic extract of *Carum copticum* fruit with morphine, using a

tail-flick analgesiometer. The results indicate that the test drug significantly increased tail-flick latency (TFL) within 2 hours following administration ($p < 0.05$). The peak analgesic effect was observed 45 minutes post-injection and was comparable to that of morphine at a dose of 1 mg/kg (i.p.). Positive outcomes in this type of analgesiometric test suggest that the antinociceptive mechanism may be opioid-related. These findings support that *Carum copticum* extract possesses a clear and measurable analgesic effect⁸. Lateef, Muhammad et al., done an In vivo study of *Carum copticum* on sheep naturally infected with mixed species of gastrointestinal nematodes where seeds were administered in three forms—crude powder (CP), crude aqueous extract (CAE), and crude methanol extract (CME)—at graded doses of 1, 2, and 3 g/kg body weight (b.w.) The maximum reduction (79.1%) in eggs per gram (EPG) of feces was observed on day 14 post-treatment in the group treated with *C. copticum* CP at 3 g/kg b.w.⁹

In a study conducted by Tanko y et al., the ethanolic extract of *Syzygium aromaticum* flower buds showed significant anti-inflammatory activity in rats by reducing formalin-induced edema at doses of 50, 100, and 200 mg/kg ($P < 0.05$)¹⁰. The in vitro anthelmintic activity of *Syzygium aromaticum* and *Melia dubia* against *Haemonchus contortus* worms of sheep was evaluated by V. Gnani Charitha et al. At the lowest tested concentration (0.16 mg/ml), *S. aromaticum* and *M. dubia* required 36.67 minutes and 79.33 minutes, respectively, to achieve complete worm mortality. These findings indicate that *S. aromaticum* possesses significantly higher anthelmintic potential—approximately six times greater—than *M. dubia*, highlighting its superior efficacy against *H. contortus*¹¹. In a study conducted by Uchaya Lopes et al "The essential oil of *Syzygium aromaticum* (EOSa) was chemically characterized by GC-MS analysis, and its biological activities—including hemolytic, anticoagulant, antidiarrheal, and antipyretic effects—were

evaluated in adult male mice; notably, fever induced by 15% *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (s.c.) was significantly reduced by oral administration of EOSa at doses of 50 and 100 mg/kg, showing efficacy comparable to that of 100 mg/kg dipyrone.¹²

According to previous studies, *Lingam* has been proven to possess antipyretic activity. In *Linga chendooram* where *Lingam* is one of the main ingredient study conducted by Austin Anoop et al., antipyretic and analgesic properties were observed. The dosage of 50 mg/kg, *Linga Chendooram* exhibited significant antipyretic activity, comparable to that of the standard antipyretic drug, acetylsalicylic acid, administered at a higher dose of 500 mg/kg.¹³ In experimental animals administration of a high dose (58.5 mg/kg) of *Linga Mathirai* resulted in a statistically significant reduction in body temperature, comparable to the effect observed with the standard antipyretic drug, paracetamol. Through Scientific evaluation of *Ashtabhairava Mathirai*¹⁴ and *Padiga Linga Chendooram*, both of which contain *Lingam* as a key ingredient, confirms their antipyretic properties.

The antipyretic activity of both Natural and Synthetic *Poora parpam* was assessed using a Brewer's yeast-induced fever model in rats. The study results indicated a significant rise in body temperature in rats that received only Brewer's yeast, compared to the control group. However, rats treated with the standard drug Paracetamol (150 mg/kg) showed the greatest reduction in rectal temperature at the 4th hour following yeast injection. A similar pattern of temperature reduction was also observed in rats treated with Natural and Synthetic *Poora parpam* at doses of 1.15 mg/kg and 2.30 mg/kg, respectively, when compared to the positive control group¹⁵. *Karpoora Chinthamnai Mathirai* demonstrated strong analgesic, antipyretic, and anti-inflammatory effects in rat models, showing efficacy in both acute and chronic experimental inflammatory conditions¹⁶.

In Ayurveda *Krumighattini* Tablet where red ochre is one of the ingredient anthelmintic activity evaluated by Shakin khan et al., *Kirumighattani* tablet, at doses of 10 mg/ml and 20 mg/ml, exhibited highly significant anthelmintic activity ($p < 0.001$) in the paralysis of roundworms. At a 30 mg/ml dose, the tablet showed significant activity in causing paralysis ($p < 0.01$), and highly significant activity in inducing death of the worms ($p < 0.001$), compared to the reference drug. The potential mechanism underlying this anthelmintic effect may involve inhibition of glucose uptake by the parasites, leading to depletion of their glycogen stores¹⁷. In Ayurveda, *Shuddha Gairika* (purified Red ochre) is administered in doses of 250–500 mg for the management of fever. Kshara Agada exhibits anthelmintic activity according to conceptual studies, with red ochre identified as one of its ingredients¹⁸.

The pharmacological screening for anthelmintic activity of LBM also evaluated by chalapathi et al., *Linga Bhoopathi tablet* demonstrated significant anthelmintic activity against *Pheretima posthuma*, showing greater efficacy compared to albendazole ($p < 0.001$). This effect was found to be concentration-dependent. The potency of the tablet was inversely related to the time required to induce paralysis in the worms¹⁹.

CONCLUSION:

After extensive research, the ingredients of LBM have been proven to possess **antipyretic** and **anthelmintic** activities. Some drugs with anti-inflammatory and analgesic effects also demonstrate antipyretic activity, as the suppression of pro-inflammatory mediators like prostaglandins plays a central role in reducing fever. Individual ingredient that possess antipyretic activity and anthelmintic activity often act through multiple biochemical pathways, resulting in enhanced pharmacological efficacy. Preclinical

pharmacological screening for the anthelmintic activity only conducted in previous studies on *Linga Boopathi Mathirai*. However, further research is warranted to explore its full therapeutic potential. This review aims to serve as a foundation for future investigations on the *Linga Boopathi Mathirai*.

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